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**ENHANCING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE CURRENT METHOD
OF ESTABLISHING TEAM MEMBERS
IN AEROSPACE COMMUNICATIONS**

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Abstract: This paper argues the efficiency of the current hiring method present in aerospace organizations for the cybersecure communications department and proposes a new improved method of finding and interviewing prospective employees.

Keywords: aerospace, project team, communications, cybersecurity, hiring process

Introductions. Establishing team members who will be successful in engineering the most efficient method of transmitting a secure space communication signal is a complex task which requires multiple methods of finding the right people for the job. Recently it has been a concern in the space industry of how to choose the most suitable employees simply based on their previous experience outside of the hiring company.

Aim. This paper aims to offer a novel way of looking at potential employees prior to hiring them in order to ensure that the most suitable specialists are hired. The method and analysis discussed in this paper is specific to the aerospace industry, however it can be used in other industries as well with the needed modifications.

Materials and methods. This paper imposes a quantitative method which goal is to develop models, theories, and hypotheses pertaining to the hiring methods specific to the space industry. The research explored in this paper is driven by various hypotheses, one of which is that the current method of hiring employees for the space communication department in the aerospace industry can be greatly improved.

Results and discussion. Current methods of hiring employees lack one crucial detail - the reality of past experience the professional has. Let us argue this based on the premise that the named professional has not yet had any professional experience in the field which they are applying for, for example, to the aerospace engineering department which is responsible for transmitting communication signals from Earth to the International Space Station. One of the reasons why that may be is because the professional worked without legal permission and thus they can not put that experience on their resume. Secondly, the professional might not want to put one of the jobs that they previously had because of a conflict with the previous company. The relationship between an employee and the employer is somewhat of a fragile one, so once it is broken, it can be a challenge to restore, even if none of the parties did anything particularly wrong [1, p. 15]. The person might think that it will hurt them in the long run if a potential employer contacts that one company with which the professional had had a conflict with. The third reason why the resume might not be the best method to judge a potential employee's performance is because the professional might not have put everything needed on the resume. For example, they might have left out an experience or a university course that they think is irrelevant to the current job, but, in fact, this is exactly what the employer is looking for in a new hire.

From that arises another question - is the employer being clear enough with what they want from a potential employee or can the method of hiring be improved on their side as well? Obviously, it greatly depends on the hiring organization, however, the majority of hiring places in the aerospace industry have a time limit for when they need a new hire to start their employment. Hence, those organizations might have a lack of time in the process of hiring someone new. That might lead to

some applicants receiving a longer of a time slot than other applicants. The concern of fairness arises from this statement as well seeing as some applicants simply might not get enough time to “show themselves” [2, p. 68]. The way that this issue can be resolved is if the employment application is divided into multiple rounds and the applicants each get their individual (of equal time) time slot. Not only having more time will give the employer a better chance to get to know the potential hire, but it will also give the professional a greater opportunity to show the employer what they are capable of as well as familiarize themselves with the employer and the hiring staff and decide if they want this organization to become their new place of work. The latter can also be done by improving the quality of questions that can be asked during one’s interview. For example, space communications is a very specific field, so the employer’s questions should also be very specific. With that, a concern arises of whether or not the employer should ask open-ended questions. For that, a more detailed scientific results report may be needed [3, p. 2].

Another base for improving the hiring process in the aerospace industry is to find out the educational background and the area of interest of the applicant. The area of interest is especially important while hiring someone new because it will genuinely show what the person likes to do most, and, therefore, would be most successful at [4, p. 8]. Educational background can reveal if the person is versatile and can, therefore, conduct multiple tasks on the job. Sometimes, the educational background can also reveal that the employees can be good at two jobs at the company or if they can be a better fit for a different job within the same company and not the job the applicant initially applied for. All these pieces of evidence are vital when choosing a new hire since it might be more challenging to fire someone after the applicant will have revealed that they are, in fact, not a good fit for the job. Then the hiring process will need to start again, thus taking the company’s time out of making new engineering developments in the aerospace industry.

Conclusions. Thus, even if the potential employee does not have the experience required for the job, they might still be able to qualify based on multiple premises. First of all, the applicants might not have put all of their experience on the

resume. Second of all, the hiring employer might not always be clear with what they are looking for in a new hire and that the employers should spend more time figuring out the questions which they will ask the applicants during the interview. Thirdly, it would be best if the hiring company devoted a time slot of equal time to each participant, therefore making the application process a fair process for every professional who wishes to apply. Last but not least, the educational background and area of interest play an important role in the hiring method as well because, theoretically, a company is more likely to hire a professional who likes their job over one who does not. In conclusion, with the improved method discussed in this paper there will need to be scientific experiments conducted in order to, firstly, show that the current method of hiring employees for a space communication job position is imperfect and, secondly, show that the improved method of hiring written in this paper will bring out the most suitable employees during the hiring process.

REFERENCES

1. Чумаченко И. В. Формирование холистической ценности инновационных проектов и программ / И. В. Чумаченко, Н. В. Доценко // Восточно-Европейский журнал передовых технологий. - 2011. - № 1(5). - С. 14-16.
2. Чумаченко И.В. Формирование адаптивной команды проекта / И.В. Чумаченко, Н.В. Доценко, Н.В. Косенко, Л.Ю. Сабадош // Управління проектами та розвиток виробництва: Зб.наук.пр. – Луганськ: вид-во СНУ ім. В.Даля, 2011. – № 2(38). – С. 67-71.
3. Rachenko, Yelyzaveta. “The Struggles of Establishing a Secure Connection Over a Network of Satellites.” *National University Journal*, 2018, p. 1, doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.13237886.
4. Rachenko, Yelyzaveta. “A Working Prototype of a Smart Cybersecure Home.” *Fairleigh Dickinson University - Metropolitan Campus Journal*, 2019, p. 1, doi:10.6084/m9.figshare.13237883.